

Stability of binary complexes of L-aspartic acid in dioxan-water mixtures

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Abstract : An electrometric investigation was made on the formation equilibria of binary complexes of aspartic acid with Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} at 303 K and an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L^{-1} . The stability constants of the species ML , ML_2H_2 , ML_2H_3 , ML_2H_4 were refined with the computer program MINIQUAD75. The stability constants of Zn^{II} complexes were found to be greater than those of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} due to pseudo inert gas configuration of Zn^{II} . The formation and distribution of different species were represented in the form of distribution diagrams. Influence of the co-solvent on the speciation was discussed based on the dielectric constant of the medium.

Keywords : Stability constant, ligand, metal, solvent, metal complex.

Introduction

Simultaneous equilibria involving essential metal ions and biomolecules like proteins and peptides are important in biological fluids. Hence the chemical speciation of ligands with metal ions has been studied in this laboratory¹⁻⁵. Calcium is the most plentiful metal found in the teeth, bones, nerve cells, body tissues, blood and other body fluids of the human body⁶. Dairy products are the most significant sources of calcium⁷. Calcium deficiency for a long period leads to osteoporosis, hypertension and other disorders⁸. Magnesium is an essential metal involved in human nutrition and metabolic reactions⁹. It is naturally found in legumes and soy products. Zinc is required for the catalytic activity of the enzymes.

L-Aspartic acid (Asp) plays an important role in maintaining the solubility and ionic character of proteins. It is popular as a drug for chronic fatigue as it plays crucial role in generating cellular energy, moves the coenzyme nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide molecules from the main body of the cell to its mitochondria, where it is used to generate adenosine triphosphate¹⁰. Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} are all essential elements in the biological system and L-aspartic acid is an amino acid, integral part of proteins and peptides. These bind the essential metal ions through aspartate residue. Hence there is a need to understand the interaction of aspartic acid with these metal ions. Hence

the speciation of complexes of Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} with Asp in DOX-water mixtures has been studied.

Results and discussion

The results of the best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants are given in Table 1. Very low standard deviation in overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) signifies the precision of these constants. The stability constants of Zn^{II} complexes were found to be greater than those of Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} because Zn^{II} has pseudo inert gas configuration whereas Ca^{II} and Mg^{II} have inert gas configuration. The complexes of metals with pseudo inert gas configuration are more stable than those with inert gas configuration.

The linear trends in $\log \beta$ values with $1/D$ (D is the dielectric constant of the medium) of DOX-water mixtures indicate that the electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium processes of complex formation.

Distribution diagrams :

Protonation equilibria of Asp in DOX-water mixtures have already been reported¹¹. Asp has two dissociable protons and one amino group which can associate with a proton. It exists as LH_3^+ at low pH and gets deprotonated with the formation of LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} successively with increase in pH. Hence the plausible binary metal-

Table 1. Parameters of the best-fit chemical models of L-aspartic acid complexes of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} in DOX-water mixtures

Temperature = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹

DOX (% v/v)	log β _{mnh} (SD)				pH Range
	ML	ML ₂ H ₂	ML ₂ H ₃	ML ₂ H ₄	
Ca ^{II}					
0.0	3.56(81)	25.14(91)	29.11(91)	32.43(97)	3.0–9.5
10.0	2.78(26)	24.14(46)	28.32(49)	32.44(32)	3.0–10.0
20.0	3.99(32)	24.84(44)	28.62(56)	32.52(58)	3.0–9.5
30.0	3.99(14)	25.13(21)	29.27(23)	32.71(48)	3.0–9.5
40.0	4.50(16)	25.89(18)	30.19(18)	33.64(41)	3.0–9.5
50.0	3.30(14)	24.46(32)	29.21(33)	32.99(75)	3.0–10.0
60.0	4.30(7)	25.43(7)	30.17(9)	34.10(17)	3.0–9.5
Mg ^{II}					
0.0	2.88(20)	24.23(21)	28.33(18)	31.71(19)	2.0–9.2
10.0	3.16(12)	23.62(48)	27.65(56)	31.11(83)	2.8–10.0
20.0	4.95(22)	25.34(28)	28.63(50)	32.83(37)	2.0–8.0
30.0	3.73(60)	24.97(6)	29.16(10)	32.97(6)	2.0–8.0
40.0	3.83(33)	24.65(11)	29.33(12)	33.34(8)	2.0–8.0
50.0	4.91(11)	25.72(11)	30.44(14)	34.67(13)	3.9–10.8
60.0	6.23(35)	26.51(12)	31.08(19)	35.53(11)	2.0–8.0
Zn ^{II}					
0.0	6.22(32)	23.84(92)	27.77(94)	31.48(79)	2.7–8.0
10.0	6.23(26)	23.95(78)	28.16(71)	32.20(51)	3.0–7.0
20.0	8.19(16)	25.04(23)	28.85(36)	32.49(20)	2.0–8.0
30.0	6.93(18)	24.75(43)	29.34(35)	33.42(34)	3.2–7.0
40.0	7.27(9)	25.05(16)	29.25(31)	33.17(24)	2.0–8.0
50.0	6.72(13)	24.22(63)	29.20(42)	33.44(51)	3.8–7.0
60.0	7.51(14)	25.81(17)	30.74(21)	35.12(14)	2.0–7.0

ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation revealed the existence of ML, ML₂H₂, ML₂H₃ and ML₂H₄ for Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II}. The formation of various binary complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Some typical distribution diagrams drawn for various complex species based on the best fit models in DOX-

water mixtures are shown in Fig. 1. At a pH below 3.0 ML₂H₄ species is formed for Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} as shown in Equilibrium 1. With increasing pH successive deprotonation of ML₂H₄ forms ML₂H₃, ML₂H₂ and ML. Fig. 1A represents the formation of Ca-Asp complexes. ML₂H₂ species is formed as per Equilibria 3 and 5. Similarly Fig. 1B represents the Mg-Asp complexes. ML₂H₂ is formed by the deprotonation of ML₂H₄ (Equilibrium 4) in this case. Fig. 1C reveals the simultaneous formation of ML₂H₄, ML₂H₃, ML₂H₂ and ML according to Equilibria 1, 2, 5, 6 and 7.

Experimental

0.05 mol L⁻¹ of L-aspartic acid (Finar, India) solution was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. 1,4-Dioxan (Finar, India) was used as received. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. Sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) of 2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Solutions of Ca^{II}, Mg^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides (0.1 mol L⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple-distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ acid (HCl) to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. Sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) of 0.4 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹². The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method¹³.

Procedure :

Elico (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01) was used for the titrimetric data. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred DOX-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) containing inert electrolyte for several days. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor. For the determination of stability constants of binary species, initially, titration of strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with DOX-water mixture of equivalent composition

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of Asp in 60% DOX-water mixture : (A) Ca^{II} , (B) Mg^{II} and (C) Zn^{II} .

as that of the titrand. All the titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of DOX-water mixtures (0–60% v/v) pH metrically at 303 ± 0.1 K. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm^3 . Titrations with different metal-to-ligand ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5) were carried out with 0.4 mol L^{-1} sodium hydroxide.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD¹⁴ was used to calculate the correction factor. The binary stability constants were calculated from the pH metric titration data with the computer program MINIQUAD75¹⁵. Correction factor and protonation constants of Asp were fixed during the refinement of binary systems.

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